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Executive Summary

WorldFAIR Milestone 6, reported here, specifies work done and being undertaken for Deliverable 5.2 (due month 20), ‘Geochemistry Methodology and Outreach’, which has the following description: “This deliverable will outline the methodology used to develop and update FIPs and promulgate knowledge of them, including publishers to ensure the quality, interoperability and reusability of data in publications”.

As geochemical data is collected on a diversity of natural and synthetic samples (rocks, sediments, minerals, fossils, meteorites, cosmic dust, fluids, gases, etc), from the Earth or other planetary bodies, there is an incredible range of analytical instruments used and hundreds of analytical techniques applied. This results in a community with many subdisciplines that produce typically ‘long tail’ data - data that are highly specific and small in volume. The community and the data produced are heterogeneous and overlaps of common minimum variables are scarce.

We conclude that developing a single FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) for all geochemical data will not be possible; rather, there will need to be multiple linked FIPs for geochemistry subdisciplines and at multiple levels of granularity. As a FIP is underpinned by FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs), many such FERs need to be publicly available or need to be published. By specifying any FER(s) that accompany each FAIR principle within the individual FIP, users of any geochemical dataset/database will have accurate documentation for each FAIR Principles, and thus enhance machine readability.

This Milestone describes progress towards developing a methodology designed to assist in defining the individual FERs required to fully describe the minimum scientific and technical variables used to describe any geochemical analysis. These FERs will enable the generation of multiple FIPs, facilitating published results to be reproduced and shared globally with sufficient metadata to make any geochemical resource FAIR for both humans and machines.

This Milestone report then discusses how the components of this methodology are being executed in the community, discusses resulting progress towards minimum common variables of samples, discusses how to make best practices for geochemical methods available online and specifies a set of vocabularies published to describe methodologies.

1. Introduction

This Milestone report addresses work currently being undertaken for Deliverable 5.2: ‘Geochemistry Methodology and Outreach’, which has the following description: “This deliverable will outline the methodology used to develop and update FIPs and promulgate knowledge of them, including publishers to ensure the quality, interoperability and reusability of data in publications”.

As this Milestone contributes to Deliverable D5.2, due in project month 20, the focus of this report addresses WorldFAIR Milestone 6. MS6 provides evidence for the Geochemistry Scientific Content component, described as “Availability of minimum common variables for sample descriptions and a selected set of geochemistry specific data types/data techniques that will be trialled at workshops”.

Geochemistry is a notoriously heterogeneous field (e.g., Klöcking et al., 2023). Analytical datasets are acquired on a diversity of natural or synthetic samples from the Earth or other planetary bodies (rocks, sediments, minerals, fossils, meteorites, cosmic dust, fluids, gases, etc), and there is an incredible range of analytical instruments used and hundreds of analytical techniques (Richard et al., 2023) applied on a diversity of sample sizes, from whole rock samples down to atomic subsamples. Further, geochemical datasets are ‘Long Tail’ (Heidorn, 2008) - small in volume, highly specific and collected by thousands of individual investigators or small teams, often across multiple organisations around the globe. The small file sizes mean that datasets can easily be locally stored and shared between groups resulting in little incentive to standardise ways of sharing and making datasets/databases interoperable online. Hence, there are hundreds of vocabularies used to describe geochemical data, and best practices for describing analytical methods are poorly defined, resulting in the Geochemistry community having few internationally-agreed protocols or vocabularies equivalent to, say, the Colour Books of the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC)¹ or the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Data Standard for Sharing Ecological and Environmental Monitoring Data (Miller et al., 2023). Developing FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) will not be easy for the Geochemistry Work Package.

However, the geochemistry community is increasingly realising that there needs to be consensus on vocabularies, geochemical standards, minimum requirements for the reporting and publication of geochemical data, and ensuring that scientific content is accurately documented (e.g., Chamberlain et al., 2021; Klöcking et al., 2023). Reporting standards have been described in the past - for example, Goldstein et al., (2014) argued that “*Access to the complete data, upon which new scientific discovery and knowledge is based, is a fundamental requirement for the reproducibility of scientific results.*” Discussing standardisation of how to access and share ‘the complete data’ in geochemistry - and therefore how to comply with the FAIR principles - is a relatively new activity

¹ IUPAC Colour Books <https://iupac.org/what-we-do/books/color-books/> [Last accessed 20 May 2023].

and it will be years before there is international consensus on all facets that make geochemical results reproducible. Best practices and vocabularies that have been published are available only in PDF format or as internal documents, and as such they do not contribute to making geochemical data FAIR-compliant, particularly for machine-to-machine environments.

FIPs are a collection of implementation choices made by a community of practice for each FAIR principle. Our conclusion is that it will not be possible for the WorldFAIR Geochemistry Work Package to create a single FIP for all geochemical data. Rather there will need to be multiple FIPs, at various levels of granularity.

To enable FAIR datasets and machine readability of geochemical data, a FIP should be associated with a repository, collection and dataset. Granularity becomes finer with each subsequent component and FIPs of finer granularity will need to include a provenance trail remaining linked with FIPs of coarser granularity. The effectiveness of a FIP relies on the publication of FAIR-Enabling Resources (FERs), objects or resources that enable FAIRer data. For example, a FER could be a machine-actionable description of the sample ID, a vocabulary used to describe an instrument, methodologies used or description schema of the data produced by that method. To be useful and enhance interoperability and machine readability of geochemical data, FIPs will need to be accompanied by the publication of hundreds of FAIR-Enabling Resources (FERs) for each of the sixteen FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016; Shultes et al., 2020).

By specifying any FER that goes with each FAIR principle in any FIP, the dataset/database user has accurate documentation of the online resources used to define any dataset/database. For the scientific content of a single geochemical dataset/database to be accurately and transparently described, the following (meta)data facets (1-6) need to be explicitly included in its description as FERs of machine actionable vocabularies and best practices.

Metadata facets (based on Goldstein et al., 2014):

- 1) Description of the sample and how it was collected;
- 2) Sample preparation method for each specific type of analysis undertaken on the sample;
- 3) The instrument used to analyse the sample;
- 4) Description of the analytical method (best practice);
- 5) Data reduction techniques applied to the raw analytical data; and
- 6) Results (including uncertainty quantification and quality documentation).

This report will first describe the methodology developed to define FERs to be used to enable the creation of explicit FIPs that go with any dataset/database (Section 2). Section 3 will describe preliminary work on the minimum common variables of samples whilst Section 4 will describe initial

work undertaken related to facets 2-6 in making best practices for geochemical methods available online and in the publication of a vocabulary that describes methodologies.

2. A Proposed Methodology to Develop and Update FIPs

Given the heterogeneity of geochemical data, achieving community agreement on minimum variables, vocabularies and semantic resources required for each analytical technique will not be a trivial exercise. It could take many years for agreement on the common variables, vocabulary concepts and best practices at an international level. However, there is an urgency to use and publish machine-actionable vocabularies that help make geochemical (meta)data FAIR, particularly from funders and publishers. Interoperability principle I2 requires “(meta)data to use controlled vocabularies that also follow FAIR principles” (Wilkinson et al., 2016) and hence to be fully compliant with the FAIR principles, multiple online vocabularies are emerging that often replicate the same concepts many times over.

2.1. Approach to machine-actionable vocabularies and convergence

To achieve a balance between meeting current requirements for online vocabularies vs. the length of time required to reach community agreement on standards for these at an international level, the WorldFAIR Geochemistry Work Package lead and OneGeochemistry board have developed a three-tiered approach (local, community, international) to making geochemistry vocabularies/ontologies and best practices FAIR and machine actionable:

- 1) We encourage repositories that have **locally** defined semantic resources, vocabularies and/or authors of papers on best practices with vocabularies to make them FAIR using the approach outlined by Cox et al. (2021), in “Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR”, which are e.g. to publish vocabularies in a stable recognised online vocabulary service (rule 8) such as [Research Vocabularies Australia](#) (RVA) and ensure each concept/vocabulary has been assigned a globally unique persistent identifier (rule 5);
- 2) We encourage groups with similar topics to begin harmonising their terms and publishing these as a **community** resource. An example of this is the work led by Stephen Richard, who compiled and harmonised a set of equivalent vocabularies on Analytical Methods for Geochemistry from the GeoX, GEOROC, PetDb and OSIRIS-REx databases and has published this [in Research Vocabularies Australia](#) (Richard et al., 2023); and
- 3) We raise awareness of groups who are actively harmonising and making vocabularies accessible as FAIR-compliant resources at an **international** level, and are working with recognised International authoritative groups such as Scientific Unions, international

associations/societies/commissions, etc., who can provide endorsement. An example of this is the OpenMindat Project², which is making one of the world's largest mineral and rock databases and provides a detailed vocabulary of ~5800 mineral names and ~3000 rock names that could be used to describe samples used for geochemical analysis. Mindat is based on standards from authoritative groups such as the International Union of Geological Sciences and the International Mineralogical Association (Ma et al., in press).

Once a vocabulary or 'best practice' resource is available online at any tier, we then encourage resource developers (or maintainers and sustainers), to form an Expert Committee to ensure controlled governance. GitHub will be used to further develop and version data standards, reporting formats and best practices (e.g., Crystal-Ornelas et al., 2021). The Expert Committee will ensure regular publication of updated, time-stamped versions of the vocabularies/ontologies to sustainable vocabulary services.

As convergence progressively takes place towards internationally-agreed terms and best practices, the size of the community using particular FERs increases, as does the ability to share data in machine-to-machine environments. Existing URIs³ initially used at either a local or community level could subsequently be redirected towards internationally accepted definitions and concepts as these become available online.

However, it is unlikely that every required term/concept will be standardised internationally. There will always be a need for some local or highly specialised reference terms, and thus a need for more than one vocabulary. For this scenario, we recommend utilising the "Bullseye" model proposed by Klump et al. (2021), whereby variables common to multiple use cases can form an inner core, with concepts from other vocabularies utilised to increase the variety of specialised terms, forming successively *less common* variable shells around the inner core as illustrated in Figure 1. In this model, each separate vocabulary is then referenced as multiple separate FERs in the FIP or, alternatively, a single composite vocabulary is published as a FER in which the source vocabulary of each term and/or concept is linked and referenced. This approach enables the parallel existence of multiple description schemas, each meeting the needs of a specific community and, wherever possible, drawing on multiple online resources that can exist on numerous globally-distributed sites (Klump et al., 2023).

Likewise, a similar process for the convergence of best practices for analytical methods is required. The Geochemistry Work Package recommends following the methodology developed by the

² EarthCube Capabilities: OpenMindat - Open Access and Interoperable Mineralogy Data to Broaden Community Access and Advance Geoscience Research

³ Uniform Resource Identifiers

International Oceans Community through their Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) website⁴ that facilitates the development, documentation and sharing of ocean best practices (Przeslawski et al., 2022).

Figure 1. A result of the “Bullseye” model (after Klump et al., 2021) applied to International Generic Sample Number (IGSN) sample registration. This model can be used as a means to assess common variables used by (sub)disciplines in order of commonality and minimum fields needed to make, in this case, a sample reusable. The inner core in dark grey shows the mandatory minimum variables overlapping for all sample registries, shell-1 in blue shows the additional recommended variables, and shell-2 in yellow represents the domain specific requirements of a subdiscipline for a specific community. Variable terms from [IGSN listed values](#) (DataCite, 2023).

3. Minimum common variables for sample descriptions

To ensure geochemical samples and datasets are FAIR, the laboratory, repository, data creator and policymaker communities need a set of prescribed minimum common metadata variables and the simplest schemas for reporting on samples and datasets. The minimum common variables associated with each data type will enable the community to develop FERs and FIPs as outlined in the above methodology. Here we discuss the sample minimum variables and commonalities of the Geochemistry Work Package proponents’ associated repositories.

3.1. Geochemistry samples domain repository minimum metadata

Representatives from the repositories participating in this Work Package are working towards the

⁴ Ocean Best Practice Site www.oceanbestpractices.org. [Last accessed 20 May 2023].

alignment of minimum mandatory fields for describing samples. Table 1 provides an overview of mandatory fields for these repositories in which the EarthChem-PetDB⁵ and the DIGIS-GEOROC⁶ repositories share exactly the same mandatory variables and are strongly aligned with the AGN-AusGeochem⁷ mandatory variables. All these repositories recommend the use of International Generic Sample Numbers (IGSNs) for samples that themselves have a specific set of variables described in section 3.2.

Table 1: Summary of the minimal variables required by each of the WPO5 participating repositories

	EarthChem – PetDB	DIGIS – GEOROC	GFZ Data Services	AGN – AusGeochem
Description of information type required to describe a sample	Information to identify, locate, and describe the samples, including IGSNs. Extra fields can be added.	Information that makes the Sample FAIR.	Requires only metadata about the dataset not samples	Sample metadata
Mandatory fields	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sample name, - Latitude, - Longitude, - Elevation (or Location keywords), and - Lithology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sample name, - Latitude, - Longitude, - Elevation (or Location keywords), and - Lithology 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sample ID, - Sample Kind, - Lithology Or - Mineral Type, - Latitude, and - Longitude

3.2 International Generic Sample Number

In order to give samples unique names that can be resolved persistently, geoscientists make use of a Persistent Identifier (PID) system, the International Generic Sample Number (IGSN). IGSNs are specifically designed PIDs persistently associating sample metadata to a unique ID (generated by DataCite⁸). While IGSNs are not always used by geochemistry researchers, geochemistry domain repositories heavily promote the use of IGSNs.

The IGSN practice and metadata schema is defined by a mature community, with specified mandatory minimum metadata variables required for each PID. In the methodology outlined previously, this minimum common variable set would then constitute the inner core (dark grey) set

⁵ EarthChem-PetDB (<http://search.earthchem.org/>)

⁶ DIGIS-GEOROC (<https://georoc.eu/georoc/new-start.asp>)

⁷ AGN-AusGeochem (<https://ausgeochem.auscope.org.au>)

⁸ DataCite is a leading global non-profit organisation that provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) for research data and other research outputs (<https://datacite.org/value.html>)

of metadata variables, shown in Figure 1. The current recommended minimum requirement for a material sample registration with IGSN includes Identifier, Creator, Title, Publisher, PublicationYear, ResourcesType and resourceType (see Appendix Table A1 for variable definitions). It is worth noting that the IGSN minimum variables closely align with those required by the representative geochemistry domain repositories shown in Table 1.

In addition to the mandatory properties (some of which are generated upon registration), IGSN also provides a set of recommended variables for material samples, which include Subject, Contributor, Date, AlternatelIdentifier, RelatedIdentifier, Description and GeoLocation, see Appendix Table B1 for variable definitions. This recommended variable set can then be represented as shell-1 (blue) in Figure 1, with each successive shell representing an increase in domain-specificity. For example, shell-2 (yellow) in Figure 1 may represent the domain specific requirements outlined by the Tephra volcanic deposits community (Wallace et al., 2022) or the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Data Standard for Sharing Ecological and Environmental Monitoring Data (Miller et al., 2023).

4. A selected set of geochemistry specific data types/data techniques that will be trialled at workshops

As geochemistry is a typical ‘long tail’ data discipline, it has many subdisciplines focusing on the acquisition of highly specific data, using many different reporting methods and generating a relatively small volume of diverse data. With community maturation, standardisation of data used with/in larger datasets and interdisciplinary compilations occurs with accompanying best practice publications. A list of these publications, shown in Appendix Table C1, has been curated and published on www.OneGeochemistry.org⁹.

This initial listing of geochemistry data standardisation publications contains both local and community-derived vocabularies and best practices. However, they currently exist in PDF formats. With none being machine actionable, none can be used as a FAIR Enabling Resource. The development of these resources into machine-actionable FERs will be facilitated by the Geochemistry Work Package through direct engagement with authors and community members in the production of machine-actionable documentation to support these pre-existing local and community publications. This activity has commenced with communication now underway between WorldFAIR WP05 and leading authors of standardisation publications.

⁹ OneGeochemistry is an international collaboration between multiple national and international organisations that support geochemistry capability and data production. Predominantly a voluntary effort, the OneGeochemistry initiative is currently run through a working group of the International Science Council’s Committee on DATA (CODATA) and receives a small amount of funding through the Horizon Europe project ‘WorldFAIR’ and from AuScope. Most OneGeochemistry activities are directly supported by the participating national and international data systems.

The alignment of groups is another way in which to start the standardisation between subdisciplines. The Geochemistry Work Package has brought together Geo.X¹⁰, GEOROC¹¹, EarthChem¹², Astromat¹³ and OSIRIS-REx¹⁴ to discuss and share information on analytical methods for geochemistry, which resulted in the publication of a machine-actionable [geochemistry methodologies vocabulary](#) on Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA), led by Stephen Richard (Richard et al., 2023). Another example is the work done between GEOROC and EarthChem to publish their joint vocabularies on RVA, two repositories represented by members of the Geochemistry Work Package. Finally, Astromat and MetBase, two cosmochemistry databases and also members of the Geochemistry Work Package, aligned their schemas and decided to merge both databases into a single one, which is more sustainable, reduces the effort of inputting data in separate databases, and allows simpler access for data retrieval.

5. Conclusions

This Milestone report outlines work towards the second WorldFAIR Geochemistry Work Package Deliverable, D5.2. As part of the second Deliverable, this Milestone set out to find data description commonalities within the many geochemistry subdisciplines. These commonalities form the basis for developing FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) for the geochemistry community consisting of FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs). Many FIPs are needed as no single all-encompassing FIP will capture the data diversity within the community. FIPs need to be developed at both coarse and fine granular levels in order to enable diverse geochemical data to become FAIR. The methodology for defining FERs that fully describe the minimum scientific and technical variables used to describe any geochemical analysis is outlined in section 2.1. We encourage local, community and international development and promulgation of machine-actionable vocabularies, ontologies and best practices.

Further, a set of recommended values for the description of samples is shown to converge between the repositories represented in this Work Package. In addition, these repositories all recommend the use of IGSN and its metadata schema with mandatory and recommended variables which can be represented in the “Bullseye” model.

With the publication of a curated set of best practices on www.OneGeochemistry.org, the commencement of active facilitation in the development of machine-actionable best practices, and the publication of a geochemistry methodologies vocabulary (Richard et al., 2023) this Work Package is making good progress towards Deliverable 5.2.

¹⁰ Geo.X (<https://www.geo-x.net/en/>)

¹¹ DIGIS-GEOROC (<https://georoc.eu/georoc/new-start.asp>)

¹² EarthChem-PetDB (<http://search.earthchem.org/>)

¹³ Astromat (<https://www.astromat.org/>)

¹⁴ OSIRIS-REx (<https://www.nasa.gov/osiris-rex>)

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Appendix A: IGSN mandatory properties in DataCite Metadata Schema

Table A1: IGSN mandatory properties for material samples, from DataCite (2023).

Metadata fields	Description
Identifier	The identifier property will be automatically populated with a DOI upon the creation of an IGSN ID. The system will assign a random DOI suffix unless a specific suffix is supplied using Fabrica or DataCite APIs.
Creator	The creator property contains a list of “the main researcher(s) involved...in priority order.” For IGSN IDs, this could be the sample collector/creator, chief scientist, curator, or even the person who deposited the sample into a repository. As a norm, IGSN ID registrants are expected to collect information about the sample owner, Principle Investigator, and/or otherwise. However, if no appropriate name is available, the property will be populated with the name of the IGSN ID Repository registrant or an appropriate standard value for unknown information from Table 11 of the DataCite Metadata Schema.
Title	The title property should include appropriate elements that would help find and distinguish a sample. The exact syntax is at the discretion of the IGSN ID registrant. Appropriate elements might include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The basic form of the object that is registered. For example, polished section, core, pulp, solution, dredge haul in a box, lot, or piece of material. - The material or materials that compose the sample. For example, water, granite, or tissue. - Local sample identifiers. We strongly recommend populating the title property with an appropriate value to enhance discoverability. If no title information is available, there is the option to fill this property with an appropriate standard value for unknown information from Table 11 of the DataCite Metadata Schema.
Publisher	The publisher property contains “the name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource.” For IGSN IDs, this should be the organisation registering the IGSN ID for the physical sample.
PublicationYear	The publicationYear property should contain the year when the sample was first made available to the research community. This is likely to be the year at the time the physical sample is registered unless the sample was released before registration of its metadata record. The DataCite Metadata Schema provides the following additional guidance for the publicationYear property that is relevant to material samples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If the date of public availability cannot be determined, use the date of registration. - If an embargo period has been in effect, use the date when the embargo period ends. - If there is no standard publication year value, use the date that would be preferred from a citation perspective.
ResourceType	The resourceType property may be populated with resource types from external ontologies or shared vocabularies. In the absence of an agreed vocabulary, the use of the terms “material sample” or “feature-of-interest” are strongly recommended to at least distinguish between these sampling concepts. A material sample is a specialisation of a larger feature-of-interest, which is typically the collection site. For example, in the Geosciences, a feature-of-interest might be a lake,

Metadata fields	Description
	tree, cross-section, transect, or borehole.
resourceTypeGeneral	The resourceTypeGeneral property is “PhysicalObject” for all IGSN IDs.

Appendix B: IGSN recommended other properties in DataCite Metadata Schema

Table B1: IGSN recommended properties for material samples from DataCite (2023).

Descriptive metadata fields	Description
Subject	The free-text subject property contains the "subject, keyword, classification code, or key phrase describing the resource." For IGSN IDs, this is the materials that compose the sample. Since materials may be categorised under different schemata, the sub-properties subjectScheme and schemeURI should also be included whenever possible.
Contributor	All institutions and people involved in a sample's workflow—from collection to archival (or discarding/destruction)—may be captured in the free-text contributor property. If contributor is used, the sub-properties contributorName and contributorType are mandatory. Note that to be included in the reference to a resource, a person or organisation must be listed in a creator property (and can then be additionally listed in a contributor property). People and organisations listed only in a contributor property are not included in the resource reference.
Date	The date property may be used to log events relevant to the physical object. The date property requires the dateType sub-property, which must be entered from a controlled list. The "Collected" dateType may be used to record when a sample was collected. At this time, there is no controlled list value for "Destroyed", which may be pertinent to your material samples metadata. Pending the potential addition of an equivalent value, we advise using a date property with dateType "Other" and "Destroyed" in the dateInformation field.
AlternateIdentifier	The alternateIdentifier property may be used to enter any other identifiers for the material sample, including local sample identifiers. For alternate identifiers that were assigned by a researcher or within a project, "local" is the default recommended alternateIdentifierType.
RelatedIdentifier	Connecting samples to one another, and to research based on them, is a primary goal of the IGSN ID. Such connections are captured through relatedIdentifier properties, which list the globally unique Identifiers assigned to related resources. It is therefore recommended that relatedIdentifier is used to the maximum extent possible and is updated on a regular basis. The mandatory relationType sub-property describes relationships between the material sample for which the IGSN ID is being registered and related resources (features-of-interest, parent samples, subsamples, datasets, publications, etc.). The relatedIdentifier property can be used to make connections that mirror sample hierarchies. Because the parent IGSN ID is a key element in IGSN ID metadata, it is recommended that a child (sub)sample identifies its parent using the relationType "IsPartOf" or "IsDerivedFrom". Vice versa, a parent sample can identify its children using "HasPart" or "IsSourceOf". Of these four relationTypes, only "IsPartOf" and "HasPart" currently create Event Data visible in the REST API and GraphQL API. See Connections to Works. Relationships to other IGSN IDs registered with DataCite services should use relatedIdentifierType DOI.
Description	It is valuable to include additional information about a sample, particularly about its "birth," in the free-text description property. If the description property is used, then the sub-property descriptionType is mandatory. Values for the latter are selected from a controlled list, with the most relevant for IGSN IDs being:

Descriptive metadata fields	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Abstract – Brief description of the resource and the context in which it was created. - Methods – The methodology employed for the study or research. For IGSN IDs, this is the collection method. <p>Both of these are important for discovery purposes.</p>
GeoLocation	<p>The geoLocation property is used to encode information on the "spatial region or named place where the data was gathered or about which the data is focused." The property can be repeated to indicate a number of different locations, and can express a location as a point, bounding box, or polygon, or simply as a free-text description through its (respective) sub-properties: geoLocationPoint, geoLocationBox, geoLocationPolygon, and geoLocationPlace.</p> <p>For IGSN IDs, this property will contain where a sample was acquired relative to the Earth or another astronomical object. Note that it may not be relevant for samples that are 'non-geographic' (e.g., a synthetic material).</p>

Appendix C: Journal publications and grouping of best practices, guidelines and standardisation for data reporting in geochemistry

Table C1: Journal publications and grouping of best practices, guidelines and standardisation for data reporting in geochemistry.

Practice Group	Title	Authors	Year +link
Quality	Global Community Guidelines for Documenting, Sharing, and Reusing Quality Information of Individual Digital Datasets.	Peng, G., Lacagnina, C., Downs, R.R., Ganske, A., Ramapriyan, H.K., Ivánová, I., Wyborn, L., Jones, D., Bastin, L., Shie, C., Moroni, D.F.	2022+ link
Repository	AusGeochem: An Open Platform for Geochemical Data Preservation, Dissemination and Synthesis.	Boone, S.C., Dalton, H., Prent, A., Kohlmann, F., Theile, M., Gréau, Y., Florin, G., Noble, W., Hodgekiss, S., Ware, B., Phillips, D., Kohn, B., O'Reilly, S., Gleadow, A., McInnes, B., Rawling, T.	2022+ link
Samples	Sample Identifiers and Metadata to Support Data Management and Reuse in Multidisciplinary Ecosystem Sciences.	Damerow, J.E., Varadharajan, C., Boye, K., Brodie, E.L., Burrus, M., Chadwick, K.D., Crystal-Ornelas, R., Elbashandy, H., Alves, R.J.E., Ely, K.S., Goldman, A.E., Haberman, T., Hendrix, V., Kakalia, Z., Kemner, K.M., Kersting, A.B., Merino, N., O'Brien, F., Perzan, Z., Robles, E., Sorensen, P., Stegen, J.C., Walls, R.L., Weisenhorn, P., Zavarin, M., Agarwal, D.	2021+ link
Rock type	Community Established Best Practice Recommendations for Tephra Studies-from Collection through Analysis	Abbott, P., Bonadonna, C., Bursik, M., Cashman, K., Davies, S., Jensen, B., Kuehn, S., Kurbatov, A., Lane, C., Plunkett, G., Smith, V., Thomlinson, E., Thordarsson, T., Walker, J.D., Wallace, K.	2022+ link
Rock type	Community established best practice recommendations for tephra studies---from collection through analysis.	Wallace, K.L., Bursik, M.I., Kuehn, S., Kurbatov, A.V., Abbott, P., Bonadonna, C., Cashman, K., Davies, S.M., Jensen, B., Lane, C., Plunkett, G., Smith, V.C., Tomlinson, E., Thordarsson, T., Walker, J.D.	2022+ link
Methods (for soils)	International Union of Geological Sciences Manual of Standard Geochemical Methods for the Global Black Soil Project.	Demetriades, A., Huimin, D., Kai, L., Savin, I., Birke, M., Johnson, C.C., Argyraki, A.	2020+ link
Methods	International Union of Geological Sciences Manual of Standard Methods for Establishing the Global Geochemical Reference Network	Demetriades, A., Johnson, C.C., Smith, D.B., Ladenberger, A., Adánez Sanjuan, P., Argyraki, A., Stouraiti, C., Caritat, P. de, Knights, K.V., Prieto Rincón, G., Simubali, G.N. (Editors).	2022+ link
Vision LowT Geochemistry	The future low-temperature geochemical data-scape as envisioned by the U.S.	Brantley, S.L., Wen, T., Agarwal, D.A., Catalano, J.G., Schroeder, P.A., Lehnert, K., Varadharajan, C., Pett-Ridge, J., Engle, M., Castronova, A.M., Hooper, R.P.,	2021+ link

	geochemical community.	Ma, X., Jin, L., McHenry, K., Aronson, E., Shaughnessy, A.R., Derry, L.A., Richardson, J., Bales, J., Pierce, E.M.	
General? Isotopes	Standards for publication of isotope ratio and chemical data in Chemical Geology.	Deines, P., Goldstein, S.L., Oelkers, E.H., Rudnick, R.L., Walter, L.M.	2003+ link
Chronology (210Pb in sediment)	Guidelines for reporting and archiving 210Pb sediment chronologies to improve fidelity and extend data lifecycle.	Courtney Mustaphi, C.J., Brahney, J., Aquino-López, M.A., Goring, S., Orton, K., Noronha, A., Czaplewski, J., Asena, Q., Paton, S., Panga Brushworth, J.	2019+ link
Chronology (U-series)	Data reporting standards for publication of U-series data for geochronology and timescale assessment in the earth sciences.	Dutton, A., Rubin, K., McLean, N., Bowring, J., Bard, E., Edwards, R.L., Henderson, G.M., Reid, M.R., Richards, D.A., Sims, K.W.W., Walker, J.D., Yokoyama, Y.	2017+ link
Chronology ((U-Th)/He)	(U-Th)/He chronology: Part 1. Data, uncertainty, and reporting.	Flowers, R.M., Zeitler, P.K., Danišák, M., Reiners, P.W., Gautheron, C., Ketcham, R.A., Metcalf, J.R., Stockli, D.F., Enkelmann, E., Brown, R.W.	2022+ link
Chronology (U-Th-Pb)	Community-Derived Standards for LA-ICP-MS U-(Th)-Pb Geochronology -- Uncertainty Propagation, Age Interpretation and Data Reporting.	Horstwood, M.S.A., Košler, J., Gehrels, G., Jackson, S.E., McLean, N.M., Paton, C., Pearson, N.J., Sircombe, K., Sylvester, P., Vermeesch, P., Bowring, J.F., Condon, D.J., Schoene, B.	2016+ link
Chronology	Interpreting and reporting 40Ar/39Ar geochronologic data.	Schaen, A.J., Jicha, B.R., Hodges, K.V., Vermeesch, P., Stelten, M.E., Mercer, C.M., Phillips, D., Rivera, T.A., Jourdan, F., Matchan, E.L., Hemming, S.R., Morgan, L.E., Kelley, S.P., Cassata, W.S., Heizler, M.T., Vasconcelos, P.M., Benowitz, J.A., Koppers, A.A.P., Mark, D.F., Niespolo, E.M., Sprain, C.J., Hames, W.E., Kuiper, K.F., Turrin, B.D., Renne, P.R., Ross, J., Nomade, S., Guillou, H., Webb, L.E., Cohen, B.A., Calvert, A.T., Joyce, N., Ganerød, M., Wijbrans, J., Ishizuka, O., He, H., Ramirez, A., Pfänder, J.A., Lopez-Martínez, M., Qiu, H., Singer, B.S.	2020+ link
Chronology	Geochron Workshop reports sponsored by EarthChem and EARTHTIME.	Walker, D.J., Condon, D., Thompson, W., Renne, P., Koppers, A., Hodges, K., Reiners, P., Stockli, D., Schmitz, M., Bowring, S., Gehrels, G.	2008+ link
Paleoclimate	PaCTS 1.0: A Crowdsourced Reporting Standard for Paleoclimate Data.	Khider, D., Emile-Geay, J., McKay, N.P., Gil, Y., Garijo, D., Ratnakar, V., Alonso-Garcia, M., Bertrand, S., Bothe, O., Brewer, P., Bunn, A., Chevalier, M., Comas-Bru, L., Csanik, A., Dassié, E., DeLong, K., Felis, T., Francus, P., Frappier, A., Gray, W., Goring, S., Jonkers, L., Kahle, M., Kaufman, D., Kehrwald, N.M., Martrat, B., McGregor, H., Richey, J., Schmittner, A., Scroxton, N., Sutherland, E., Thirumalai, K., Allen, K., Arnaud, F., Axford, Y., Barrows, T., Bazin, L., Pilaar Birch, S.E., Bradley, E., Bregy, J., Capron, E.,	2019+ link

		<p>Cartapanis, O., Chiang, H. -W., Cobb, K.M., Debret, M., Dommain, R., Du, J., Dyez, K., Emerick, S., Erb, M.P., Falster, G., Finsinger, W., Fortier, D., Gauthier, N., George, S., Grimm, E., Hertzberg, J., Hibbert, F., Hillman, A., Hobbs, W., Huber, M., Hughes, A.L.C., Jaccard, S., Ruan, J., Kienast, M., Konecky, B., Le Roux, G., Lyubchich, V., Novello, V.F., Olaka, L., Partin, J.W., Pearce, C., Phipps, S.J., Pignol, C., Piotrowska, N., Poli, M. -S., Prokopenko, A., Schwanck, F., Stepanek, C., Swann, G.E.A., Telford, R., Thomas, E., Thomas, Z., Truebe, S., Gunten, L., Waite, A., Weitzel, N., Wilhelm, B., Williams, J., Williams, J.J., Winstrup, M., Zhao, N., Zhou, Y.</p>	
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